

Traces of the Riemann zeta function; use of CAD.

Author: Dante Servi Mail: dante.servi@gmail.com

Abstract.

I have been studying the traces resulting from three formulations of the Riemann zeta function for a year, I think I learned about the zeta function of Riemann enough not to have the slightest doubt that it is true.

This article is dedicated to those who would be interested in analyze with the CAD the traces in question, but are held back by the fact of not knowing what characteristics the CAD must have and above all how get PARI-GP results formatted to be rows of CAD command.

Premise.

This article can be considered an appendix to the preprint "Traces of Riemann zeta function on the complex plane" available at the following link <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8026759>

As in the aforementioned article, I call (a) the real part of (s) and (b) the coefficient of the imaginary part, therefore $s=a+bi$.

To obtain the necessary results to report the traces in the CAD issue I use PARI-GP, which I recommend; it's free, easy to install and use, it's fast, powerful, flexible...

PARI-GP can be downloaded from the website <https://pari.math.u-bordeaux.fr>

In fact CAD doesn't require many hints, I think they will turn out the suggestions I provide on the use of PARI-GP are more useful for many.

The examples I present in this article are for only one formulation of the zeta function, what I think of this formulation and of the other two that I have studied can be found in the reference article, of which I point out the recently added sections 10 and 11.

$$\zeta(s) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \frac{1}{n^s}, \quad \Re(s) > 1$$

1. Characteristics that the CAD must have.

- You don't need a 3D CAD, the traces in question develop on a plane two-dimensional, which should be the Complex plane; I remember that though the Complex plane was derived from the Cartesian plane assuming that the (y) axis was the imaginary axis and the (x) axis was the real axis.
- It must have a command line that can accept that an unlimited number of text strings are pasted, or must accept commands via scripts.
- It must allow you to work on the four quadrants of the Cartesian plane.
- Regarding the number of decimals that can be set for the plus odds the more the better, but this is a surmountable problem.

2. PARI-GP functions and commands useful for obtaining the data needed by the CAD.

To get the necessary results from PARI-GP, I created myself a function personalized; the basis is the PARI-GP function $\text{sum}(X=a, b, \text{expr})$ from which I obtained the following, for the formulation that I have chosen.

$$Z(f,s)=\text{sum}(n=1,f,1/n^s)$$

This function gives the value of $Z(f,s)$ for $n=f$, so it's a useful one starting point, but for the CAD it is necessary to be able to extract all the points of the trace or part of the trace of interest.

The following command lines for PARI-GP get the values of $Z(f,s)$, for (n) from $(f1)$ to $(f2)$; as data require (a) , (b) , $(f1)$ and $(f2)$.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=
b=
s=a+b*I
f1=
f2=
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s))))
```

The custom function that does the calculations to get the points relative to the vertices of the trace, has the drawback of starting over from $n=1$ for the calculation of each new point.

For large final values of (n) the waiting time can become excessively long.

For these cases I somehow solved the problem with the following command lines.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=
b=
s=a+b*I
f1=
f2=
fb1=f1-2
fb2=f1-1
Base=Z(fb1,s)
Z(f,s)=Base+sum(n=fb2,f,1/n^s)
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s))))
```

The required data are always (a) , (b) , $(f1)$ and $(f2)$, I note that must be $f1 \geq 2$.

The PARI-GP command line allows you to paste a series of strings of text previously written with an editor, which can be Notepad's Windows or similar.

If there are characters in the text that are not valid for PARI-GP they will get errors, but sometimes a result that isn't formatted the way you want.

PARI-GP does not allow you to directly copy text but it can write its results in a file, you can also use the to activate writing command `default(log,1)`.

With this command PARI-GP writes the results of the calculations to the file `pari.log` located in the root folder where it was installed.

If desired, it is possible with the command `default(logfile,<path><filename>)` assign the desired path and file name, writing in the assigned file must still be activated with the `default(log,1)` command.

You will find that PARI-GP does not overwrite an existing file, it adds in tail to possibly existing lines, so after the content is been used, you need to delete or rename the file.

Example of command lines ready to be transferred to PARI-GP.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=1/2
b= 43.32707328091499951949612217
s=a+b*I
f1=0
f2=round(b/Pi)
default(log,1)
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f,s)) ", " imag(Z(f,s))))
```

The result must be as follows; only the initial part of the first row can be different.

```
gp > for(f=f1,f2,print(real(Z(f,s))", "imag(Z(f,s))))
0,0
1.000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000000,0.E-56
1.1313960734336165916204626372527917803,0.69479138731437052562368683345095863648
0.61816491393532252480158259355955560131,0.95922873386997709434144881191751228069
0.15269477016286725248392327852961113138,1.1418144541671838479182656416028772258
0.51739946125094719247713923402177209630,0.88298924616311755079936859987722025109
0.26623411125798828766592676513493134049,0.56114668584894604277559507246272577253
-0.063186667376594888687367586884626309982,0.37583858170633762938478805474566422974
-0.25120660247796639568636852630433906930,0.076424981473355482578773342239042201545
-0.057727489651373000777998913957274444771,-0.19500999050141687351126042219852367210
0.17002280006149654644488322588983753718,0.024375071742355748605032089601012447530
-0.12414041964635508239438779885659557066,0.090534659711153741734729335601611318996
0.066470878559482269535689113928325007782,-0.12626171094485765551344376202154909875
-0.040202059491024795274084800416928519933,0.12975383782269201787438036944816468703
0.045263818446785109560047871762432781861,-0.12347363923477662273598896350861675304
```

When there are several zeros at the beginning of the part in the results decimal, PARI-GP uses scientific notation and this normally creates problems for the CAD.

If it is a question of a few cases they can be corrected manually, if they are many can use an artifice to get around the problem.

The artifice is to insert a multiplier in the last row of command; the trace will be larger depending on the multiplier.

If the accuracy of the CAD permits, the trace can then be scaled, with base on the origin, to bring it back to the correct size and position, otherwise we must limit ourselves to taking them into account.

Obviously the same multiplier must act on both coordinates, here is an example.

```
Multiplier=1000000
for(f=f1,f2, print(real(Z(f,s))*Multiplier ", " imag(Z(f,s)) ))*Multiplier)
```

It happened to me in a few cases that I needed to increase the default precision by PARI-GP, just in case here's how.

\p n Where (n) indicates the number of digits to display but also acts on the calculation precision.

3. Checking and adapting text for CAD.

The text to be transferred to the CAD must start with the line containing the command, which can be “line” but can also be “pline” or other equivalents accepted by the CAD.

As already highlighted, CAD does not normally accept numbers in notation scientific, in conclusion the first three lines in the example case should be as follows.

```
line  
0,0  
1.00000000000000000000000000000000,0
```

The first few times I think you'll want to get full traces (up to $\text{round}(b/\pi)$), later you may want to get only the part of relevant trace.

In the second case, I recommend adding (except in particular cases) in addition to the command the second line as well, so you get a line that starts from the origin and connects to the relevant part of the trace.

The reason is to easily locate a part of the trace that can also be very small and have a certain connection with the origin.

As with PARI-GP, the CAD will almost certainly require that the rows of command do not contain unnecessary special characters, therefore for the necessary modifications it is necessary to use an editor equivalent to Notepad.

4. Data transfer to CAD.

First you need to be able to locate and highlight the origin of the plan.

It should be noted that CAD allows you to draw figures with dimensions of several millimeters, the traces we want to obtain will be figures a few millimeters in size.

Normally the CAD allows you to set the limits of the drawing and of adjust the initial display to the set limits.

It is advisable to set limits that delimit a window of a few millimeters and chosen so as to have the origin in the center of the screen; the first sometimes perhaps it is better to draw the axes of the plane.

The command followed by the coordinates of the points is a classic that should be compatible with any CAD; with the correct command lines as described, the CAD must therefore create the following trace.

If the CAD does not accept that an unlimited number of text strings, it needs to accept scripts, in this case the file created by PARI-GP will probably have to have the extension required by the CAD for script files.

If the CAD accepts scripts it must have a command that allows you to locate the file and run the script.

In the article of which I have provided the link you can find several traces, for which I indicated which formulation of the zeta function is been used, the values of (a) and (b) and also the initial values of (n). and trace endings.

For those wishing to try to make Figs. 6 and 7 in the article above, maybe it needs some more help.

Here are the command lines that allow you to get the two parts that make up the trace represented in Fig. 6.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=1/2
b=10000.0653454145353147502287213889928
s=a+b*I
f1=3083
f2=3183
default(log,1)
for(f=f1,f2, if(f/2 > truncate(f/2), print("line\n" real(Z(f,s)) "," imag(Z(f,s))), print(real(Z(f,s)) "," imag(Z(f,s)) "\n")))
```

$(f/2) > \text{truncate}(f/2)$ forces the vectors starting in (n) odd to be drawn, so they end in (n) even.

```
Z(f,s)=sum(n=1,f,1/n^s)
a=1/2
b=10000.0653454145353147502287213889928
s=a+b*I
f1=3083
f2=3183
default(log,1)
for(f=f1,f2, if(f/2 == truncate(f/2), print("line\n" real(Z(f,s)) "," imag(Z(f,s))), print(real(Z(f,s)) "," imag(Z(f,s)) "\n")))
```

$(f/2) == \text{truncate}(f/2)$ forces the vectors starting in (n) even to be drawn, so they end in (n) odd.

I note that in both cases PARI-GP inserts a number in scientific notation. Remember that you must always delete all the lines that precede the first "line" command.

In these two cases, the following two lines should not be inserted at the beginning.

```
line
0,0
```

Obviously in both cases if the CAD requires a command other than "line" it is necessary to correct the last of the command lines that I put a disposition.

This is the link that corresponds to this preprint.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8218694>

This is the link to the Italian version of this preprint.

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8218690>